

Living with *Haru4Kids*: Study on children’s activity and engagement in a family-robot cohabitation scenario

Gonzalo A. García¹, Guillermo Pérez¹, Leigh Levinson², J. Gabriel Amores³, Gloria Alvarez-Benito³, Manuel Castro-Malet¹, Mario Castaño-Ocaña¹, Marta J. López-González de Quevedo¹, Ricardo Durán-Viñuelas¹, Randy Gomez⁴, and Selma Šabanović²

Abstract—*Haru4Kids* (H4K) is a system that emulates the physical, social, family-oriented robot *Haru*, designed with the goal to cohabit with children in their home for extended periods of time. Seven families kept H4K for two net weeks in their homes. Throughout this period of cohabitation, we collected user logs comprised of the children users’ head angles, the rotation angles of the platform, and the actions taken by H4K as well as captured images which were afterwards hand-annotated to estimate user engagement. We report the trends of these external metrics that we collected during every session of interaction. We also developed an annotation tool and report the Engagement Level Metric we chose to estimate child engagement throughout interactions “in-the-wild.” Overall, our platform offers a feasible system that can engage with children while also allowing us to monitor their engagement and behaviour throughout each interaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the leading questions in the field of child-robot interaction (CRI) is “how do we keep children engaged?” In research labs, children are invited to interact with robots in a specific, controlled environment; but “in-the-wild”, such as in their homes, children have more freedom to choose when and how to interact with a social robot [1].

In this paper, we introduce the *Haru4Kids* (H4K) platform designed for children’s use in their home. The platform features an avatar of the robot *Haru* [2], [3] displayed on a tablet screen (an *iPad*) which is held up by a table-top rotating stand, the propose of which is to keep the tablet always facing the child, even if they move. An advantage of this approach is that children are more familiar with tablets, so we can fully focus on their reactions and likes of the different activities and behaviours that H4K displays.

This work builds on previous studies which introduced the table-top social robot *Haru* to children and explored how to align its design with UNICEF’s *Policy Guidance*¹, such as recognizing children’s concerns about privacy and fairness when engaging with robots [4]. Beyond this, the

main principle guiding *Haru*’s design is to achieve a “balance between human expectation, surface appearance, physical affordance, and robot functionality” [5], [2]. Therefore, we monitored the level of engagement of the children while interacting with the robot avatar. The aim of the preliminary tests presented here is to use H4K as a test-bed to gauge the degree of acceptance of *Haru* by children, with a main focus on attaining their long-term engagement and interest.

In a separate report [7], we describe the methodology in great detail, the self-reported experiences family members had with H4K during the cohabitation experiment and reflect their changes in comfort sharing specific information with *Haru* and their perception of the agent. In the present paper, we report the external metrics with which we monitored the usage profile and the level of engagement for the duration of the experiment. Overall, we enrich the previous findings with this publication which takes into account children’s actual behaviour towards and with the robot.

II. BACKGROUND

A. Engagement Estimation

The research area on how we humans interact with social robots has been explored in recent years [11]. Often in child-robot interaction research, researchers try to operationalize children’s attention and level of immersion with an activity, often defined as “user engagement” during interactions [46], [48], [47]. Monitoring this quality of interaction in the context of children and robots is a main goal of this work, but defining this concept is not uniform across the field. One way to describe this quality is by identifying children’s *level of engagement* throughout an interaction. As defined by O’Brien [12], User Engagement (UE) is “a quality of user experience characterized by the depth of an actor’s cognitive, temporal, affective and behavioural investment when interacting with a digital system.”

There are self-report tools for UE measurement, such as the User Engagement Scale (UES) that have been used in a diverse range of digital domains [13]. Also, there are a number of research studies which dealt with the automatic, real-time estimation of UE, mainly in the area of online education (e-learning) [16], [17] and for children in the autistic spectrum [18], [19], [20], [21]. Some are based on processing certain physiological signals such as electroencephalogram (EEG), electrocardiogram (ECG), or electro-dermal activity using either specific equipment or

*This work was supported by *Honda Research Institute*, Japan

¹*4i Intelligent Insights*, CREA Buiding, José Galán Merino Street, 41015-Seville, Spain {g.garcia, g.perez, m.castro, m.castano, m.lopez, r.duran}@4i.ia

²Indiana University Bloomington, Bloomington IN 47401, USA {lmllevins, selmas}@iu.edu

³Department of English Language and Linguistics, Universidad de Sevilla, 41004 Sevilla, Spain {galvarez, jgabriel}@us.es

⁴*Honda Research Institute*, 8-1 Honcho, Wako, Saitama 351-0114, Japan r.gomez@jp.honda-ri.com

¹<https://www.unicef.org/globalinsight/media/2356/file>

wearable devices [14]. However, these approaches are often too intrusive, cumbersome, and complex to be applicable to young users. Even though some new approaches use non-disrupting techniques, such as thermal infrared imaging [22], these methods are not easily integrated into children’s spaces “in-the-wild.”

Therefore, we chose two methods, both based on visual media, which are unobtrusive and inexpensive [23], one of them being automatic and the other, manual. This external, hybrid (manual and automatic) approach features higher time resolution (granularity) and is more reliable, less labor-intensive, and less vulnerable to biases than self-reported metrics [14], [15]. Namely, we have chosen to estimate the UE from the angle of the user’s face with respect to the iPad screen (automatic; for details, see [26]), in addition to collecting hand-annotated engagement levels from pictures. We also conducted a brief study of the CRI based on the dialogues they maintained.

B. Long-Term child-Robot Interactions

In addition to the challenges in the definition of engagement, sustaining a child’s engagement over a long period of time is no trivial task. A survey conducted on long-term experiments with robotic platforms reveals the risk of a novelty effect where children may lose interest in the platforms over time [6]. In addition, researchers have found that game adaptation is not enough to sustain long term engagement [8]. Kanda *et al.* [25] report that establishing friendly relationships with the robot yielded longer use. There are also some studies about estimation of engagement in CRI with neurodivergent populations, which have also called for a diversification of “engagement” across different scenarios given an increased success with engagement models [9]. As such, we are in the pursuit of an engagement measure that can help grapple with the novelty effect in CRI, as well as providing a human-in-the-loop approach to defining engagement for long-term interaction.

III. RESULTS FROM INITIAL PILOT STUDY

Previously to the present study, we ran an initial, 2-week pilot study with the aim of checking the feasibility of the system *in-the-wild*, and acquiring children’s first impressions and feedback on how they interacted with and accepted this platform. The main result was that children’s engagement during the first days with the agent was substantial, but then the usage rapidly decreased and was just marginal for the rest of the testing period. This kind of disenchantment is not uncommon when introducing new technologies, and is consistent with sentiments in the retrospective feedback of children in the current study [7]. However, the source of disenchantment can vary widely from finding a robot less useful to a robot not meeting expectations [1]. To better identify when children were interested in the robot, in this study we focused on continuously monitoring their level of engagement while using H4K, for later analysis off-line.

Fig. 1: *Haru4Kids*: (a) iPad supported by rotating-tabletop stand, and (b) high-level technical description of the system.

IV. HARU4KIDS PLATFORM

The H4K platform consists of a Haru avatar displayed on an iPad supported by a rotating stand (Fig.1a). The app is designed to use several *Apple*-specific libraries. At the highest level of abstraction, the application is divided into seven main modules: User Interface, Conversation Manager, Vision Manager, Central Controller, Settings Manager, Logging, and Stand Manager (Fig.1b). In addition, the Conversation Manager makes use of some services from the *Cloud*. The Central Controller acts as the coordinator of the app’s behavior, interacting with other modules and accessing the cloud as needed.

V. METHODS

1) *Participant families*: A total of seven families from the South of Spain participated in the study. We used convenience recruitment, making use of researchers’ contacts and word of mouth. Our research was approved by Indiana University’s Institutional Review Board #14363 for human subjects research. Caregivers provided their written, informed consent and children ages 7 or older provided their written assent. In total, H4K engaged with 14 children ($n_{male} = 9$) between the ages of 6 and 13 ($\mu_{age} = 9.6$). Besides one family with an only child, the other six families had at least two children. Taking into account periods of time when the children were not at home (vacations or living in multiple households), the robot cohabitated with each family for an average of 20 days ($\sigma = 5.9$, $\max = 27$), yielding a net period of two weeks. Researchers went to each family’s home, and after gathering consent, set-up the system, explained to the parents how to configure the level of information sharing, and gave a brief introduction on how to use the platform to all family members. However, children were left to explore H4K’s characteristics and features on their own.

2) *Haru4Kids Activities*: H4K features a number of entertainment-educative activities to engage children:

- **Storytelling**: H4K tells a story while displaying specific illustrations on the screen.
- **Gusano Loco (“Crazy Worm”)**: H4K tells the user to suggest words within different categories and after com-

piling a list of words, H4K fits them in an incomplete story and tells the –usually humorous- resulting story.

- **Detective:** A list of words is given, and children need to identify the one that does not match.
- **Would you rather ...?:** H4K presents two silly options from which the user has to choose one; e.g., “Would you rather have three eyes or two noses?”.
- **Jokes:** H4K tells three child-friendly jokes in a row.

This list was created by a team of neuro-psychologists and speech therapists collaborating with the *Spanish Association for the Effects of Cancer Treatment (AEetc²*, Seville, Spain) with the main aim of stimulating children’s brains, by targeting different cognitive functions.

Future content and activities can be easily added by JSON files. After each activity, H4K suggests another one, and also accepts direct requests of specific activities from the child.

A. Data Collection

1) **Image and Audio Capture:** We collected pictures of the users’ face interacting with H4K in order to identify which content children were most interested in and when they attended to it more steadily. For the 6 out of 7 families that opted in for image collection, we captured one picture with the frontal camera of the iPad for every second of interaction, yielding 19,688 photos. The captured image was displayed in real time as an inset in the iPad screen, so that the user was aware of the image recording.

Audio was recorded only when the child was expected to say something (e.g., answering a direct question).

Images and audio of the interactions were stored locally on the iPad for later processing. None of these user’s personal data were stored on the cloud at any moment, respecting the privacy of the children and their families. They were allowed to delete at any time the pictures and/or audios taken so far.

2) **User Logs:** All the events occurring during the execution of the application were logged as text entries in real-time, both locally in the tablet and on the cloud by *Cloudwatch (CW)*, from *AWS Cloud*. Each log entry is composed of a timestamp (date and hour, up to tenths of a second) and a codified text defining the type of event with its associated parameters. The event types are:

- Actions taken by H4K (e.g., display a drawing), and those by the user (e.g., request an activity);
- User’s head angle (UHA) components: roll, pitch, and yaw, estimated by *Apple’s Vision* framework, as some studies have shown that the level of attention of a human-machine interaction can be estimated by the angle of the user’s face with respect to the screen [26];
- Current rotation angles (pitch and yaw) of the rotating stand (Stand Cumulated Angle (SCA)), as it follows the child; under the assumption that the more a child moves (hence, higher SCA), the less attentive they are.

The logs generated by each family are identified by a random key unknown to everyone except one member of the research team. From those logs, we afterwards extracted

objective, continuous information about the user-robot interaction that can be used for dialogue quality measurements [28], as those described in the *PARADISE* framework [29].

B. Data Processing

Once the systems were collected from the participating families, we uploaded all the gathered data to our local, highly restricted-access server. Then, we created a usage profile, and manually annotated the captured images.

1) **Usage profile:** While processing the logs, we divided each family’s global daily activity into sessions, defined as the time between the app was started until it was shut down (H4K went to sleep). A comprehensive table corresponding to each session was created to track the following information: Date, Session ID, Activity start and end timestamps, Activity Duration, Activity Type (e.g., Story), Activity Item (e.g., “David and Goliath”), and whether it was actively requested by the user or proposed by H4K.

From the CW logs, we also extracted information about usage that was generated in real time during the interaction, such as the number of times users responded to H4K, but those responses were not recognized as a proper answer (issue labelled as “Out Of Scope” –OOS); e.g., if Haru asks for a color and the child answers “car”.

2) **Engagement profile estimation from users’ pictures:** We created an *Engagement Level Metric (ELM)* based on hand-labelling users’ pictures in 4 levels. That ELM could estimate children’s engagement, and be used as a support to design more engaging activities in future applications. Before starting the annotations, the 12 annotators attended a one-hour training seminar given by a certified psychologist to learn about the annotation process. They also received a 6-page reference guide that detailed the ELM which follows the descriptions of [27], [16]. The 4 levels were the following:

- **High Engagement:** Face illuminated, eyes focused on the screen, upright posture without unnecessary actions.
- **Low Engagement:** Expressionless face with eyes mainly focused on the screen; posture mostly upright and without unnecessary actions.
- **Low Disengagement:** Slightly frowning or tired facial expression, looking away from the screen; sometimes leaning back or forward with unnecessary actions (e.g., touching their face). Eyes barely open.
- **High Disengagement:** Frown or tired facial expression, frequently looking away from the screen and yawning, frequently losing their posture or leaving the place. Eyes completely closed, or face is out of frame entirely.

The nearly 20K pictures collected across all 6 families were divided into two equally sized ensembles and randomly assigned to a group of six annotators each (randomly grouped). Sets of 5 consecutive pictures each were shown each time to the human annotator by the annotation tool developed by us and hand-coded each set of 5 pictures by the 4-level scale. The annotators saw just the child’s face, with no information about the activity that was being used when the pictures were taken. Each child of the family was assigned a label, allowing H4K to be used by more than

²<http://asociacionetc.org/>

one child, although the ELM was assigned for each set of pictures to just the child directly interacting with Haru.

Our tool is endowed with the following features for real-time monitoring of the level of attention of the annotators themselves: (i) at random intervals (following a normal distribution with $\mu = 15$ minutes and $\sigma = 5$ min), a test null picture (e.g., a teddy bear or a doll) was shown within the current 5-picture set, so that if the annotator labelled it (not realizing there was a test, null picture), a warning message popped up and the annotation process would be paused. Additionally, (ii) for each set of pictures, the reaction time of the annotator was recorded for later processing.

C. Assessing Annotation Quality and Reliability

Two different sets of coefficients were used for to evaluate the quality and reliability of the annotations:

- Coefficients specific for inter-rater agreement assessment: (a) Krippendorff’s α [30], (b) Cohen’s κ [31], and Cronbach’s α [10].
- General coefficients for series comparison: (a) Pearson’s Correlation Coefficient (r) [32]; and (b) the Root Mean Square Deviation (RMSD), which was normalized by $(y_{max} - y_{min})$; 3 in our case), obtaining the ratio of the difference, $RMSD_{norm}$. Its complementary $(1 - RMSD_{norm})$ could be understood as an agreement metric, or at least a *similitude*. That is, e.g., a 34% $RMSD_{norm}$ could be interpreted as a 66% similarity.

D. Additional measures for engagement estimation

- **UHA**: we made a correlation study of each of its three components and the ELM. It has been reported that a yaw angle in the range $[-12^\circ, 12^\circ]$ is related to an engaged state, corresponding a 0° angle the user looking straight to the iPad (and hence to its camera) [26].
- **SCA**: We calculated the cumulative rotation that the stand went during the 5 seconds corresponding to each set of pictures and studied its correlation with ELM.

VI. RESULTS

A. Usage profile

Figure 2 shows the usage time, accumulated for all the families for the two-week experiment. Note that from day #10 on, the graph collects the data of just one family. The usage in general was low, having only one family 15 net days of use, and a family minimum of three days. As for time of use, the total was 18 hours and 22 minutes, with a family minimum of 53 minutes and a maximum of 4 hours and 55 minutes. There were a total of 126 sessions.

As for activity usage and preferences, Fig.3 shows the amount of times each of the activities were started. We distinguish between those times where the user actively requested a specific activity (user-driven interaction; red bars) and those proposed by H4K and accepted by the user (Haru-driven interactions; blue bars). It can be seen that the majority of the actions were user-driven. We observed that once the children got to know the existence of the different activities, they started being more proactive, making specific

Fig. 2: Evolution of the average, global time usage by day of experiment. Inset: individual families behaviour.

Fig. 3: Activities usage (amount of executions).

requests. The first day, the ratio of requested versus suggested activities was a 33%, and increased steadily until the last day, reaching a 85%.

The most demanded activity was *Joke*, followed by *Story*, and then by *Gusano Loco*, which is in agreement with what was reported by the children themselves in [7].

B. Engagement profile

The most objective measure of how attentive a user was when interacting with the platform was based on studying their profile of responses to H4K’s questions and requests, which we have reported elsewhere [40]. Figure 4 shows a table with such data extracted form the CW logs, in which we consider that the child responded correctly to the interaction if they gave a concrete, expected answer (*Response* column) or made a direct request to start another activity (*Others* column). We consider that the child did not respond as the system expected when they did not answer at all (*Silence*) or gave a response not pertinent to the ongoing interaction (*Out Of Scope –OOS* column). We can see that, on average, the children properly responded in interactions with H4K a 69% of the times ($\sigma = 13.8$); the highest ratio of no responses was to the small talk (Yes-No questions that are part of H4K’s chit-chat feature), which includes some rhetorical questions that do not expect answer. All the other activities that require input from the user show a similarly high level of response.

From here on, results are based on the **hand-labelled pictures of the interactions**; therefore, they are less objective than the above-mentioned automatic, dialogue-based engagement estimation measures.

Activity	Total Interact.s	Response	Others		No Response
			Requests	Silence	OOS
Small talk (Yes / No)	435	40%	16%	37%	7%
Small talk (Multiple-Choice)	63	65%	10%	14%	11%
Detective	94	66%	2%	21%	11%
Would You Rather	105	76%	1%	17%	6%
Gusanos Locos	623	76%	1%	10%	14%
Total:	1320	63%	6%	20%	11%

69%

Fig. 4: Users responses statistics (OOS: *Out of Scope*; see main text for details).

Metric	Averages for:		Ranges for:	
	Group I	Group II	Group I	Group II
Krippendorff α	0.36 (0.13)	0.52 (0.05)	0.42 -- 0.27	0.43 -- 0.32
Cohen κ	0.29 (0.07)	0.28 (0.08)	0.33 -- 0.22	0.30 -- 0.25
Cronbach α	0.83	0.82	0.82 -- 0.83	0.81 -- 0.82
Pearson r	0.52 (0.05)	0.47 (0.08)	0.55 -- 0.48	0.50 -- 0.43
Similitude [%]	74.5 (2.7)	73.6 (1.1)	77.1 -- 70.6	74.8 -- 72.3

Fig. 5: Inter-Annotators agreement coefficients. Averages: mean (std); Range: max – min; for Cronbach α , range is the confidence interval. *Similitude* := $(1 - \text{RMSD}/3)[\%]$.

1) *Pictures annotation quality assessment*: Once all the images were annotated, we computed measures of inter-annotator agreement (see section V-C), and realized that two annotators (one at each group) had extremely low levels of agreement with the other annotators. Hence, we removed the labels of these two annotators, as we could not consider them valid. In the remaining of this work, the results are based on the annotations of the remaining 10 annotators. Figure 5 shows their values for the agreement metrics: the average for each group (and its corresponding standard deviation), and their ranges (in the case of Cronbach’s α , the range is the confidence interval).

For the socio-psychological realm in which we are operating, the values of the coefficients are in the range of fair-moderate [31], so we can have a reasonable trust in the labels given by the 10 selected annotators (see *Dicussion* section for details).

2) *Engagement study by activity using ELM*: In order to further ensure the validity of the manual labelling, we selected from the labels for each set, only those in which at least three annotators agreed in its ELM, which was a 79.0% of the sets (1,632 in total). Afterwards, we considered the ELM of each set as the most-voted one, ELM_3 ; as each group had five annotators, there was no possibility of tie. Also, we calculated ELM_4 using only the sets in which at least four of the annotators labelled them with the same ELM (32% of the sets); and ELM_5 , considering only the sets for which all the five annotators agreed (just an 8% of the sets).

Figure 6 shows the average ELM_3 for those activities for which there was annotators agreement (\overline{ELM}_3). It can be seen that the mean \overline{ELM}_3 across all families (right-most bar of each activity) is quite similar among activities, being slightly higher for *Detective*, *Would you Rather* (WYR), and *Gusano Loco*. On the other hand, as Fig.7 shows, average ELM_3 by family suffered a slight decline as time passed by.

Fig. 6: Average ELM_3 per activity and family.

Fig. 7: \overline{ELM}_3 evolution with time, per family.

The ELM_3 of all the activities were significantly different when compared pairwise using a t-test, with a 95% confidence level ($p < 0.05$); except for the activities pair WYR–*Joke*. With a 99% confidence level ($p < 0.01$), only *Story* was significantly different to all the other activities, being the rest significantly different to other three; except activity WYR, which was different only to *Story*. That test further ensured the validity of the ELM_3 .

The list of activities ordered by decreasing average most-voted ELM, \overline{ELM}_3 is: *Detective*, WYR, *Joke*, *GusanoLoco*, *Story*. The difference between each consecutive pair was around 5%, yielding a difference between the highest (*Detective*) and the lowest (*Story*), of 20%. We repeated that same analysis using \overline{ELM}_4 , and we obtained the same ordering as with \overline{ELM}_3 . Furthermore, with \overline{ELM}_5 , the results were very similar, just that *Joke* and WYR swapped places, which is not surprising, as the ELM_3 of pair WYR–*Joke* did not show statistical difference even at 95% confidence level.

3) *Other engagement metrics: SCA and UHA*: The correlation study carried out with **SCA** over the \overline{ELM}_3 values using Pearson’s correlation, gave as a result an extremely low correlation, for all its two components: 0.07 for yaw and -0.03 for pitch.

As for **UHA**, we found significant correlation only for the pair ELM_3 –UHA absolute yaw angle (head rotation by the neck axis, eye gaze moving toward a shoulder): -0.43, which is a high value. Its negative sign indicates that the further the user’s eye gaze was from the screen in the horizontal plane, the smaller the ELM_3 value got.

VII. DISCUSSION

A. Use of an avatar

Pop *et al.* found that, at least for children suffering from Autism Spectrum Disorders (ASD), using an embodied social robot to implement social story intervention was more effective than the computer screen for improving the independence of expressing social abilities for the participants [41]. However, in this study, we have opted for an avatar rather than for the physical Haru robot because we wanted to be able to deploy in a fast and robust way several platforms in different homes, and to ensure that no technical issue affected the experiments during the cohabitation weeks. This arrangement allowed us also to test different configurations with a higher flexibility, while keeping the same activities and behaviours of the real robot.

B. Objective measures

In this analysis, we opted to consider user logs and annotated images. However, children’s vocal responses are also indicators of children’s attention (see Fig.4), which could be quite useful for future research, even though within the OOS cases there could be some specific situations in which the Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) gave false negatives values; that is, if a child gave a proper answer, but the ASR was not able to understand it, the answer of the child would have been misclassified as OOS.

There are indeed some improvements to be made in ASR for children’s speech in order to make it a more reliable tool to be used as a sole means for evaluating CRIs [43]. In addition, although a time-stamped analysis was not carried out to link OOS cases with user disengagement, it is possible that a lack of understanding from the robot contributed to children’s disengagement and eventual end of a session. It is worth noting that the usage profile was calculated as the *global* usage within each family; not individually.

C. ELM validity

We used an *ELM* defined by hand-annotating the pictures of the interactions to estimate user engagement. There already exist several annotation tools for labeling pictures taken during observational studies, including some free, open-source ones (*e.g.*, ELAN software [42]). However, the tool we created for this study gave us full control on features such as picture display, annotation output format, and flexibility with inserting annotator monitoring and attention controls. Being able to tailor the tool to our goals will also allow us to benefit from the tool in future analyses for engagement estimation.

Even though there are not exact rules about the limits to consider as acceptable an inter-rater agreement for the different coefficients that we have used [33], there is some general agreement about the following interpretations: Krippendorff’s own interpretation for his α was that values below 0.667 normally indicate to discard the data [34]. However, his α could be considered a kappa-like metric [35], such as Cohen’s κ , for which the generally accepted, although arbitrary limits are: values below 0, no agreement;

0–0.20: slight agreement; 0.21–0.39: fair agreement; 0.40–0.59: moderate agreement [36]. As for Cronbach’s α values, they are normally considered as high –and hence acceptable– from 0.7 [37].

Therefore, our *ELM* values displayed in Figure 5 show, from Krippendorff’s α perspective, low reliability; from Cohen’s κ , fair-moderate agreement; and from Cronbach’s α , fairly high agreement for both groups of annotators.

It is worth noting that both α and κ are measures that try to remove from the coincidence ratio those agreements that happened by chance [38]. In doing so, some real agreements could be classified as due to pure chance if, for example, one label is much more frequent than the others, which is applicable for our data [44], [45]. That is, α and κ are “pessimistic” measures that may underestimate the real level of inter-rater agreement. In addition, we should keep in mind that “almost all agreement metrics make the assumption of independence, which is why they should be used with caution” [38].

On the other hand, *ELM* Pearson’s r values were in the range 0.43–0.55, which can be considered as strong in psychological research [49], although they could be regarded as low-moderate in health-related research [39].

Therefore, taking into account all the information mentioned above, together with the high level of similarity found by the RMSD-based metric (71–74%), and the fact that the activities showed significant differences in their ELM_3 , made us consider *ELM* as a valid estimation of engagement.

D. Other engagement metrics: SCA and UHA

As for the other engagement metrics, we found a negligible level of coincidence between the engagement level estimated by *SCA* and that by ELM_3 , which can be due to some shortcoming of the *SCA* metric itself. However, on the other hand, *SCA* gives a very detailed, fine-grain view of the user’s current level of fidgeting, which could be quite useful for future studies monitoring the level of calmness of the child, mainly in case of some conditions such as attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) [50].

The high and negative correlation found between ELM_3 and *UHA* (-0.43), means that human annotators interpreted as lack of attention when the user was not looking straight to the screen (0°) and that, the further the child’s eye gaze was with respect to the screen (bigger angle), the less attentive they were considered to be. This is in consonance with what we all assume in our daily life: if someone we are talking to does not look straight at us, we estimate that that person is not paying full attention to us. In the case of H4K, this could introduce a bias, as a user need not be looking at the screen always in order to be fully engaged to the robot; *e.g.*, when listening to a story, H4K shows just a few static images. For future works, we could fine-tune this measure depending on the *expected* level of attention of the child to the screen.

E. Implications of the results for future designs

If we order the list of activities by their respective $ELM_{3,4,5}$, their precedence does not match with that or-

dered by their usage profile (amount of executions; see Fig.3 for details). This is not a contradiction, just due to *ELM* measuring how engaged a child is during an activity; and the usage, how many times it was executed. Hence, those measures could provide us with a different perspective when designing new activities for children: if we aim at designing highly-engaging activities, we will use *ELM* as a guide to select the most engaging activities. For tasks that we need to be carried out by the children with higher frequency, our decision parameter will be its usage profile.

F. General Discussion

Other researchers have struggled before us to sustain children’s attention after the novelty effect wears off. Our results are in line with those findings [51]: during this study, there was a clear decline of activity. However, although there was a decrease in user activity within the first few sessions, in this iteration there was less consistent drop-off across participants with respect to the pilot study.

We recognize that overall use of the platform was not widespread (see, *e.g.*, Fig.2). There are many potential reasons for why a child may or may not decide to interact with the platform everyday, but it could be related to the limited nature of content or personalization. Specifically in our case, it may be related to a lack of embodiment of the app-based system. There may be perceptual differences between our social agent and physically embodied robots. In fact, children’s perception of our platform differed as we reported in [7]. Though our platform afforded robustness, its lack of physical presence is a disadvantage.

G. Future work

For the next iteration of H4K development, we plan to add more, diverse activities, including ones with a more interactive component and that require the child to pay attention to the screen more often, allowing us to better evaluate their level of engagement. We would also like to involve different populations, both geographically and culturally, as well as children in special conditions such those bedridden in hospitals, because research has found that social agents can help children suffering from long-term illness develop skills, but that it can also be involved in improving children’s quality of life in other ways [52]. We will also include other contextual factors into engagement, such as the presence of other family members during H4K use.

The two-week period of cohabitation let us test the feasibility of the platform for longer term relationships in the home. For the next round of experiments, we aim to have the platform for at least four net weeks in the homes of the participant families. We know that adaptability is a great way to sustain a children’s engagement across long-term interactions, and therefore we plan to develop more collaborative storytelling.

A long term goal will be to embed these activities into the physical Haru robot. Equipped with a data-driven model for measuring children’s engagement as initiated by the annotation and *ELM* defined in this work, the Haru platform

could be more personalized and interactive for children’s long-term interactions.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

In spite of the inherent difficulties of working with robots in the wild, *Haru4Kids* has revealed itself still at this point of its development as a useful tool for monitoring in real time and in a continuous fashion the behaviour of the children when interacting with a robot. This, together with the software tools we have created for analysing the resulting data, makes this platform quite useful as a researching instrument for Honda Research Institute studies, as well as for general psychological studies such as those related to attention or developmental disorders. This work contributes to a growing body of literature that aims to mix objective and subjective measures of user engagement to create more meaningful and exciting child-robot interactions.

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